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Lessons Learnt from Japan to Improve Pescatourism Focusing on Justice

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Lessons Learnt from Japan to Improve Pescatourism Focusing on Justice

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Abstract:

Small-scale Fisheries (SSFs) are often undervalued and receive insufficient attention from governments and the public worldwide, including coastal areas in Japan. The common problems SSFs are encountering include the aging population, low income, and environmental degradation. However, Pescatourism, a popular type of fishing tourism in Europe, has the potential to alleviate the vulnerabilities and follow the current sustainable regulations in Japan. Meanwhile, Japan is expanding its Umigyo industry, allowing fishers to carry out economic activities utilizing all regional marine-related resources. It advocates that SSF communities grow their tourism industry as an element of Umigyo, which is a similar tourism style to Pescatourism to make tourists experience the fishers' lives and living in SSF communities. My study aims to examine the role of justice in the governance of Japanese SSF in the context of Pescatourism operations. In doing so, my case studies, with observations, interviews and focus groups, first describe the existing Umigyo initiatives in five ports of Shizuoka and Miyagi in Japan. Then, the extent of justice is reflected by the efforts of the current Pescatourism market in these ports in addressing the emerging vulnerabilities. My study then analyzes the current governance arrangements, including existing values and institutions, power dynamics for benefit allocation among stakeholder groups, and SSF fishers' degree of satisfaction through interaction with the Pescatourism governance in Japan. This study can help reflect the importance of justice in SSF tourism governance and its possible adaptations to Pescatourism not only in Japan but elsewhere.

Keywords: Small-scale fisheries • Umigyo Tourism • Pescatourism • Vulnerability • Viability • Justice

1. Introduction

Currently, there is an increasing concern of the sustainable coastal business with appropriate governance in the world. Pescatourism, as a kind of sustainable fishing tourism, is assumed to be a potentially sustainable solution because it allows fishers to work in fishery-related industries rather than fully rely on fishing. The blue economy activities, which encourage sustainable use of marine resources to ascend economic benefits in Asia-Pacific Island countries, focus on not only fisheries but also tourism (Bhattacharya & Dash, 2021). Authentic Pescatourism involves being on board traditional boats with professional small-scale fishers, but Japan's spectacular form of Cormorant fishing that performs catching fish by trained cormorants while spectators watch from other boats is also regarded as Pescatoruism (Piasecki et al., 2016). More precisely, according to Li and Lou (2018), "Umigyo is defined as a series of economic activities carried out by community people centered on fishermen, for answering diverse needs on marine and coastal use, utilizing not only fishery resources but also all kinds of regional marine related resources." This kind of tourism includes experiential fishing, recreational fishing guidance, and responses by fishermen's cooperatives (Goto & Takayoshi, 2017), while research categorizes Umigyo activities into five types: to stay, to play, to buy, to eat, and to learn based on the perspective of the value of the fishing communities (Lou, 2013/2022).

The governance of the coastal region has experienced a long development, while there are several fields of justice. Nayak (2022) has shown the Quadruple (In)justice during the historical process, including the historical and ongoing (in)justice (about ideology), unexpected and unusual (in)justice (about shocks),

recurring and anticipated (in)justice (about natural disasters), and Blue Growth-related (in)justices (about the trend of institutional arrangements). In other words, the basic indicators of the degree of justice are ideology development, responses to shocks, prevention and relief of disasters, and governance empowerment. The following objectives guided this research:

1. To examine the extent to which Pescatourism exists in Shizuoka and Miyagi, Japan.
2. To assess the existing vulnerabilities of SSFs in the study site.
3. To examine the potential role of Pescatourism in addressing the vulnerability.
4. To analyze how the fisheries governance arrangements facilitate Pescatourism as a driver of viable SSFs.

SSFs encounter different types of vulnerability, including socioeconomic, socioecological, and marginalization factors. Nowadays, there are several indicators to assess vulnerability, such as an indicative Vulnerability Capacity Index considering the material, institutional and attitudinal vulnerability (Weeratunge et al., 2014). In terms of the factors of socio-ecological resilience, Lee and Park (2021) list the individual, social, and physical environments as variables in a social-ecological model. Likewise, according to Islam and Chuenpagdee (2022), SSFs' vulnerability factors are in the biophysical, economic, social, technological, and governance fields, while biophysical and governance are most commonly vulnerable. SSF is a vulnerable group due to continuous poverty, and their economic performance is low because of the uneven allocation of the benefits from their fisheries as well as the pressure from globalization and climate change (Schuhbauer & Sumaila, 2016). However, top-down resource management disempowers fishers with untransparent language (Nayak et al., 2014). This results in low communication efficiency and understanding between the government and SSFs.

In terms of governance and its justice concerns, it is highly related to the right of speech, fairness, and equity. Research concerns the maintenance of equitable allocation in justice procedures with ways to resolve unfairness, the increase of the awareness of justice through visible values, principles, institutions, and instruments, and a well-organized hierarchy with well-thought orders (Nayak, 2022). More specifically, ocean-based economic development sometimes requires additional transparency, decision-making rights and information to include key stakeholders (Bennett et al., 2021).

2. Methodology

This thesis employs a case study approach in the lens of qualitative study, consisting of several stages to achieve a comprehensive understanding of Pescatourism in Japan and its impact on SSF communities. The case study was designed to evaluate a program, event, activity, process, or individual in-depth through archives, interviews, and observation (Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Eisenhardt, 1989), which aligns with the understanding of Pescatourism's context of operation in the study site. Initially, a comprehensive literature review of fishery-related ecotourism at the research site was conducted to understand the current application of Pescatourism in Japan. This review involved sourcing journal articles and books by using keywords from the research fields followed by inductive semi-structured interviews. These interviews were analyzed inductively to identify features for testing different perspectives of vulnerability context concerns and livelihood vulnerabilities within SSFs. The final stage involved focus group discussions which were used to elicit more insights and explanations as participants discussed topics with others from the same stakeholder group.

The case study was conducted in Japan, which has a popular fish culture in Japan. According to Bestor and Bestor (2014), sushi, as a food covering rice/ rice bowl (Don), fish, and vegetables, has been an ethnic specialty that has successfully expanded to the whole world since the 1970s. Lou (2013/2022) demonstrates that there is a fishing village per five or six kilometers along the coastline in Japan. The case study material narrows from the scale of Japan to the specific locations: Mochimune Port, Yui Port, and Tagonoura Port

in the central Shizuoka Prefecture, Higashiizu in the southern Shizuoka Prefecture, and Higashi Matsushima in Miyagi Prefecture (shown in Figure 1). Each case represents the situation of Umigyo Tourism in Japan to some degree, but their similar and special features or representativeness are explained later as the basis for opinions.

Figure 1

Locations of Five Study Sites in Japan

The snowball sampling was extremely suitable for this research as Japan's fishermen are not used to being interviewed by unknown people. The adapted sampling size of this research's qualitative individual semi-structured interviews included 18 local SSF staff (SSF fishers, FCA staff, restaurant staff, and seafood processors), 5 marine academic professors (the mixture of environmental specialists and academics), and 3 officials. Similarly, 2 officials, 2 fishers in the restaurant field, and 5 Umigyo tourists joined the focus groups. They are shown as Table 1 and Table 2 below. Data from these case studies was qualitatively coded using MaxQDA software to discover emerging themes and concepts and gather details of these themes and concepts to address the research objectives.

Table 1				
<i>Interviewees</i>				
Locations Conducting Interviews	SSF Staff	Prefectural/Regional Staff	Marine Professors	Academic
Mochimune (Central Shizuoka)	6 Interviewees: Processor: 102101/120701 FCA Staff: 102102 Fishers: 102103/120701/ 102104	3 Interviewees: 112801 120801 121801		
Tagonoura (Central Shizuoka)	1 Interviewee: FCA/Restaurant: 102501			
Yui (Central Shizuoka)	4 Interviewees: Restaurant: 110801 FCA Staff: 120603 Fishers: 120601/120602			
Higashiizu (southern Shizuoka in Inatori)	4 Interviewees: FCA: 120802 Fishers: 120803/120804/ 120805			
Higashi Matsushima (Miyagi)	3 Interviewees: Restaurant: 120101 Fisher: 120102/120201	/		
Tokai University in Shizuoka	/	/		5 Interviewees: Tourism Field: 112801 Umigyo Field: 120401/121501/ 122601/011601

Table 2	
<i>Focus Groups Participants</i>	
Stakeholder Groups	Number of Participants
Restaurant Owners	2 Participants --O20231130 (01)/ O20231130 (02)
Prefectural Officials	2 Participants --R20231130 (01)/ R20231130 (02)
Umigyo Tourists	5 Participants —T20240116(01)/ T20240116(02)/ T20240116(03)/ T20240116(04)/ T20240116(05)

3. Results

The current justice of Umigyo Tourism is with more positive reviews, and next, there will be explorations in detail of its various advantages in practical development. In order to display more intuitively, the analysis will exhibit the existing (in)justice phenomena before showing the current Umigyo Tourism achievement and three orders one by one.

3.1 Recognized In(Justice) in Traditional Fishing Industry

The vulnerabilities are the indicators that allow for the issues to be explicit to certain scales or contexts to explain the urgent problems in JSSFs and the necessity of considering Umigyo Tourism. Beyond a general understanding of the vulnerable context of JSSFs, many classification analyses are applied to find the connection between different factors. This includes (1) the shocks, trends, and seasonality in the vulnerability context, (2) affected resilience, and (3) threatened livelihood.

3.1.1 Vulnerability Backgrounds

Several sources in the vulnerability context are causing the traditional JSSF business to earn less, with a trend of a shortage of JSSF successors. Firstly, the fishing schedule is seasonal in Japan. It is universal to set a long closed-fishing season for coastal Japan [112801], while the temperature also limits the aquaculture period every year [120101]. There are also many shocks in Japan. In terms of the national scale, Japan witnessed or is witnessing health shocks with severe natural disasters and pandemics which took several years to recover [120101 & 112801], economic shocks with long-term stagnation until now [121501], worse population trends with more aging workers [121801], resource trends suffering from more serious global warming and degraded ecological environment (Li & Namikawa, 2020; Takayanagi, 2020), and the governance trend with less focus on the primary industry Lou (2013/2022). Among them, the self-restraint policies during Covid-19 exacerbated economic growth for roughly 2 years. In addition, with the regional natural shocks, such as pollutants, more predators, and lower nutrition, the national global warming results in the change of habitats of some fish species and the reduction of fish catch by JSSF fishers [120201].

The seasonality of fishing seasons has a neutral impact on JSSF, as implementing closed-fishing seasons during decades worsens fishers' short-term benefits but improves the long-term biodiversity for fishers' ongoing benefits. The most serious ecological impacts are the ongoing climate change trend that brings more warm currents and a temperature rise, followed by more factors affecting fish health and the loss of regional biodiversity (Takayanagi, 2020; Hirose et al., 2017). Socially, the JSSF suffers from negative stereotypes and insufficient support for the primary fishing industry [120101], which makes it a dead-end career in the public's perception [102103]. Economically, under the background of the long-lasting bubble-

economy harms and oil-price increase, the worse biodiversity leads to a lower income for JSSF households, and the 3.11 Earthquake and COVID-19 have led to periods of income stagnation. Overall, the economic problem impacted by the severe biodiversity shrinkage is the most urgent problem for the lower successor retention rate.

There has been some loss of resilience due to the vulnerabilities above:

1. With the worst economy and environment, the worse domestic condition with a lower fish stock leads to the worse trend of some JSSF households' primary income.
2. When the challenges of JSSF occur, there is no effective political support with sufficient emphasis on reversing the trend of shrinkage in the primary industry.
3. As the motivation to be JSSF successors is lower, fishery-related culture and craft are gradually disappearing in Japan.
4. The current successor-shortage trend has reached a point where it threatens the survival of some fishing villages.

With the loss of resilience as a result of the vulnerability context, the livelihoods of the JSSF fishers and community development worsened, reaching the urgent extent of the vanishment of some JSSF communities (shown in Figure 2). Well-being, in the context of small-scale fisheries can be understood at material, relational, and subjective levels. Due to the impacted material well-being, including the weaker natural, financial, and physical capitals, there is a lower quantity of food with food potential risks, shrinkage in fish diversity, decreased primary income, failure of some aquaculture cases, unsustainable inflation of some fish species, and the forced merger of some FCAs. The influence of rational well-being, with the worst human and social capitals, leads to successor shortage as the young people go to big cities [120804], frustration due to the severe natural disasters [120101], shortage of local staff and services in FCAs (Delaney, 2015), and JSSF communities' weaker connection between the public [120804]. Finally, the current degree of subjective well-being has led to the demise of SSF households due to more cases of JSSF disbanding, with the subsequential possibility of declining local fisheries-related businesses.

Figure 2

Relation of Vulnerability Factors in JSSF

3.1.2 JSSF Market and Efforts toward justice in the Umigyo Tourism Development

The degree of Pescatourism's existence in study sites in Shizuoka and Miyagi, Japan, is gradually growing. Umigyo Tourism's development from over 1300 years ago to the present has been regulated and normalized after Umigyo became a formal political act (Piasecki et al., 2016; Lou, 2013/2022). Different communities are using their strategies, sometimes with unique innovations, to operate Umigyo Tourism at different stages, and the diverse activities that match the demand are shown in Table 3. The progress of Umigyo Tourism is steady, with more support received. Each port has a different scale of Umigyo Tourism business, but JSSF fishers and distinctive activity diversity degrees in different ports, including the strategies of education, the existence and forms of marine cruises, fishing, morning market, and guesthouses, unique species, and the strategies and targets of promotion operate different forms of Pescatourism.

	Mochimune (Central Shizuoka)	Yui (Central Shizuoka)	Tagonoura (Central Shizuoka)	Higashiizu (Inatori)	Higashi Matsushima (Miyagi)
Matched Demand Characteristics (Niche Market)	Food/Education	Food/ Student Education/ Natural Beauty/ Unusual Leisure	Food/ Natural Beauty/Education	Socialization and Natural Beauty/Food/	Socialization and Natural Beauty /Food/ Education/ Unusual Leisure
Popular Target Species	Shirasu; Tuna	Shirasu; Sakura Shrimp; Tuna	Shirasu; Tuna	Kimme fish and Tenkusa; Tuna/ Lobsters	Oysters and Nori
Outstanding Product Characteristics	Shirasu Restaurants: School Trip	Sakura Shrimp Restaurants/ Cooking Class/ Marine Cruise	Shirasu Canteen (Certificate)/Marine Cruise/Marine courses	Buffet canteen/ Marine Cruise/Recreational Fishing/Morning Market	Restaurants/ Guesthouses/ Marine Cruise/ Workshops
Activities Not Open to The General Public Yet	Marine Cruise	/	/	/	Rock Fishing
Special Promotion	Brand Effect (Processing Factory/Branding)	Brand Effect (Branding); Art (Learning outcomes)	Brand Effect (GI Certificate)	Online Videos	Workshop Outreach; famous people's photos; Green Destination 2022
Sustainability Stage	Developing	Developed but recovering	Developing	Developed and under adjustment	Developed but recovering

Source: The data are from observation, semi-structured interviews with fishers, FCAs, and academic specialists in five study sites, and a focus group with officials.

Although Umigyo in Japan is a synonym of Italian Pescaturism, Umigyo Tourism is different from Pescaturism thanks to its development process (initial definition, the most urgent problems encountered, and drivers), (2) different experiences of outdoor activities (lower stimulation level, food services not on boats, and lack of toilets to maintain a long-time cruise), and (3) the application of indoor education (with students as target market and promotional channels).

3.2 Meta-(third) Order Support to Umigyo Tourism

Due to Umigyo Tourism's social contribution, Japan's marine values and cultures, and the urgent desire for marine protection, JSSF receives a deep concern for marine governance and justice. Meta order, which enhances the social-ecological system through images, values, and norms, focuses on the principles and

norms of rationality (Nayak, 2022). In Japan, the JSSF's importance has been recognized by the government, so there is increasing support for it, especially for overcoming the urgent successor shortage. This Section explains Figure 3 about how the JSSF applies Umigyo Tourism to receive more benefits through its social contribution and spread of image and value.

Figure 3

Umigyo Tourism's Expected Benefits Through Social Contribution and Value Spread

Source: Adapted from Li & Lou (2018); Lou & Yu (2022); Nouzari et al. (2020)

Umigyo Tourism is more like a pioneer that figures out the social value's efforts for the successor maintenance, especially when the current purposes of Pescatourism and Umigyo tourism differ due to the different social conditions. When both types of tourism realize the mutual benefits of the environmental, economic, and social outcomes, the priority is the economy for Pescatourism and the social perspective for

Umigyo Tourism. Italy's focus is on the alternative income channel through social cohesion and economic vitality of the local cultural heritage when there are declining living resources (Piasecki, 2016; Gravagnuolo & Angrisano, 2013). Although some research (Saba, 2013) points to the maintenance of successors as one of the outcomes, its purpose was to prevent the young generations from being kicked out of the sector. In other words, the SSF was charming for the young fishers, and some of them are passionate about staying in the fishery-related industry even though the fishing industry faces challenges. Compared with Italy, the lack of successors in SSF communities in Japan is the prior problem over the economic problem. Four out of five study sites strongly insist that the successor problem is the most severe. The fishers in these communities see Umigyo tourism as a prior alternative project to retain the young successors who did not want to inherit due to the lack of SSF's charm. Thus, the primary goal of Pescatourism was social cohesion and economy when most of the young successors remained, while the main emphasis of Umigyo tourism was the maintenance of SSF successors from the outflow.

3.2.1 JSSF's Social Contributions for Fishers

The birth rate continues to drop in Japan (Yagi et al., 2022). The birth rate continues dropping in Japan (Yagi et al., 2022). According to Nakatani (2019), the traditional social environment and family values were ruined by a long-term economic recession after the burst of the economic bubble and with globalization, which was opposite to the traditional lifelong full-time employment, and the proportion of those over 65 is expected to grow from 27.7% of the total population in 2017 to 38.4% in 2065. In addition to the trend of an aging population, the outflow of young generations has worsened the fisheries industry due to a well-known stereotype of fisher life in Japan: tiring, poor working environment with a lower salary. A Shizuoka Official [121801] showed more precise and recent data that the number of fishers continuously decreased from 22,654 in 1963 to only 4,814 in 2018 in Shizuoka and from 62,993 in 1963 to 15,170 in 2018 in Japan, and around half of the fishers in Shizuoka Prefecture are over 59 years old in 2023. At the same time, Nakatani (2019) highlights the fear in 1991 when the economic bubble burst, which led to many failures to find full-fledged employment or regular jobs with appropriate income. A fisherman in Mochimune [120702] sighed, "As more fishers are pessimistic about the future economies, they do not recommend their children to be fishers in the future." Therefore, the continuous drainage of successors due to the loss of confidence threatens the existence of fishing communities.

When cultural inheritance encounters bottlenecks, Pescatourism's presence will show its effect. As a fisher [120101] pointed out that more attention should be paid to the fun and cool image of being a fisherman, Umigyo tourism facilitates the diversity of the fishers' work to match the desire. Recreational Umigyo projects, especially the experience village, not only bring self-employed households' considerable extra income from tourists but also enhance residents' recognition of the local culture, tradition, industry, and belief to love their hometowns for cooperation (Lou, 2013/2022). Likewise, in addition to the economic efforts and the value creation of regional resources, the trawling project leads to fishers' sense of accomplishment in their jobs, more active communication within the department, and youth customers' interest in the ocean (Lou, 2013/2022).

JSSF is a place that offers a healthy lifestyle and interaction. Most forms of external links are for students in ports because a Tagonoura FCA staff [102501] explained that the Japanese government provides some support for access to schools. Yui FCA staff [120603] hoped some of these students would be impressed enough to come to Yui or other JSSF communities again. Another phenomenon of the external link is to leave the community to describe the JSSF communities to attract people to travel there. In particular, the Osakana Study Group, in Hichijo Island, Tokyo, outreaches its business to schools in other places to have food courses, which gives fishers opportunities to popularize the value and stories of the fish [120401]. With the contact, according to a fisher [120201], customers who are interested in learning about SSF or Nori normally contact him on social platforms. As audiences are given the chance to share their own insights [120101], tourists [FG 20240116] felt that the discussion with fishers is the gate to better learning about the communities. Consequently, diverse and interesting activities through active interactions among fishers,

fishing cooperative associations (FCAs), and the prefecture governments have helped participants gradually negate their original stereotypes of fishers' living habits and imperceptibly make them understand the local value through more active interaction and activities, which turns fishers from a so-called dead-end job to a meaningful career.

3.2.2 JSSF's Efforts on Value and Culture

JSSF fishers are the best candidates to share nature-related values. Compared with Large-scale Fisheries (LSFs), which are profit-oriented with Rich companies' investments leading to a higher environmental cost, SSFs are like social entrepreneurship with long-term strategies because the fishers belonging to the community are more likely to love their home and surrounding nature by paying more attention to environmental improvement and setting the rules of the catch limits [120101]. In other words, JSSFs' pure love for the ocean makes them more convincing in their role as the representatives of the ocean, calling for environmental protection so as to inherit culture.

Fishers can bring the public a correct recognition of the marine ecosystem. For example, according to some fishers [120101 & FG 20231201], there are some misconceptions that beauty is limited to picturesque scenes. However, these fishermen explain that true beauty encompasses the richness of fish species. They highlight this by pointing out the nearby coasts, showing that water does not necessarily indicate a rich ocean ecosystem.

Meanwhile, JSSF alleviates the food security problem through a self-sufficient strategy. Fisher [120101] pointed out the serious food security problem, and genetically modified food cannot be a sustainably effective solution because it will cause a larger gap among countries when they have different funding foundations. In contrast, according to a marine specialist [120401], Umigyo, which aims to use fish resources more efficiently, can reduce waste, such as cooperating with inland schools to sell fish lunch boxes to solve the excess seafood problem as a strategy of promoting the JSSF communities. When it comes to Umigyo Tourism specifically, a Tagonoura FCA [102501] staff highlighted that the canteen was built to handle the extra fish, as there used to be so many fish available that exceeded the demand, and unsold fish would be thrown away. In other words, JSSFs' pure love for the ocean makes fishers more convincing in their role as representatives of the ocean.

3.2.3 JSSF's Marine Education as Publication of Values

Education is a prior channel for the spread of JSSF values and social contribution, especially when the government, FCAs, and fishers undertake marketing activities to build relationships with educated groups. The schemes of the experiential learning programs for schools (elementary, middle, and high school) were introduced in around 2002, while the implementation was in 2006, and the long-term stay for elementary schools has been held since 2008 (Li & Namikawa, 2020). Specialist [011601] also confirmed, "It is widespread for most SSF communities to operate and guide the school visits near their ports." There are several cases of both education through indoor education and outdoor experiential learning and education outside the communities through workshops and outreach. Therefore, long-term collaboration with schools has made environmental education in JSSF communities a norm in coastal Japan and alleviated the restriction to business during the closed-fishing seasons.

In terms of education in the communities, research explained that traditional Pascatourism focused on boarding activities on boats before fishermen's households expanded to more activities held by them in the fishing communities, such as village visits and guesthouses (Piasecki, 2016; Saba, 2013), which is similar in Japan with the government's supports on marketing (Li & Lou, 2018). However, based on a fishers' experience [120101], "The mere experience on the boats is more likely to make tourists feel interested and excited, while the education effort is very limited. Thus, it is important to operate indoor classes as a

supplement.” As fishers have the decision-making right to design and operate indoor education activities under co-management, which gains the government’s support, their Umigyo Tourism pursues a more effective learning effort.

Indoor education is not only a formal form of learning in a classroom. Yui has more innovation in its teaching style, such as its Fish Cooking Class. A fisherman teaching it [120602] described the steps and facilities, “There are four workstations with sinks, each of which can accommodate about eight people. Fishers first demonstrate how to use a knife to scrape fish scales and cut fish’s heads before cutting fish meat alongside the fishbone. After chopping the fish into small pieces, participants can finally process the sashimi by themselves and process some slices of Japanese silver fish before frying them with flour. Of course, fishers bring support for the learners when they cannot handle the fish well. Then, participants can eat their fish with rice and miso soup. There are seasonings, including soy sauce, scallions, and ginger.” This more interactive cooking class has been known well by nearby ports as an iconic project [120602]. Meanwhile, outdoor education activities are mainly marine cruises. Watching the coastal scenery and feeling the breeze are ordinary marine cruise activities, with some chances for passengers to watch fishers catch fish, which is more popular during festivals.

3.3 Second Order (the responsibility of the institutions and organizations)

The analysis of the second order, which corresponds to the importance of institutions and rules, is to explore the degree of the structural dysfunction and distributive inequities (Nayak, 2022). As Japan has the potential and foundation to develop more Umigyo projects, it is meaningful to list the stakeholders in other Umigyo projects in other cities as a possible guide for the Umigyo development in Shizuoka and Miyagi. This section discusses the new missions and the corresponding benefits/efforts and costs of different common stakeholder groups currently, as Umigyo brings more diversity to fishing as a so-called original and essential job.

The drivers behind these two kinds of tourism are not completely the same. According to Piasecki (2016), the main groups that carry out Pescatourism activities are sometimes fishers, fishermen cooperatives, and consortia. In contrast, Umigyo Tourism is more non-profit without the involvement of the financial groups [011601]. As a result, fishers and FCAs in Japan have a high autonomy in carrying out activities without concerns about capital intervention.

3.3.1 Fishers

SSF fishers in Japan have a relatively higher empowerment. Fishers represent a crucial body of coastal governance due to their on-the-spot experiences, role as implementers of Umigyo activities, monitoring activities, active engagement in coastal governance, and little cost on building new organizations for coastal governance, while their knowledge of aquatic resources brings various coastal stakeholders a contact point for participation (Li & Lou, 2018; Li & Namikawa, 2020). There has been a legal guarantee of FCAs to ensure the fishing rights to coastal areas since 1948 in Japan's Fisheries Law, which is responsible for access to resources and income to strive for economically valuable rights for SSF households (Delaney, 2015).

In terms of Umigyo Tourism, the diverse activities include the B&B (food and accommodation), the outdoor activities on boats, the indoor education, and the selling of souvenirs. Fishers, who can be instructors and leaders of workshops in experiential learning programs, get paid by the program operator (Li & Namikawa, 2020). According to the Umigyo tourists [FG 20240116], the lively atmosphere, as a result of the fishers’ enthusiasm, is successfully conveyed to tourists, and some of the tourists, become friends with the fisher, even though they were joining the program for the first time. In addition to the operator role, fishers can also be planners and deciders of activities. Guesthouse businesses are initiated and decided by Miyagi fishers themselves [officials, FG 20231130], and fishers discuss whether or not to go fishing on the day,

landing targets, fishing locations, and fishing times, and to issue commands and orders during operations, as well as become the decision makers of whether they can start or restart some marine activities, such as the experiential education activities after the 3.11 Earthquake in Yui [120601]. Similarly, fishers, instead of the government, set their local rules of the catch limits [120101]. Although fishers can gain some money after participation in the tertiary industry, they are responsible for some costs. For example, regarding security concerns, they should take care of vessel inspections [121801], life vests, and insurance (Li & Namikawa, 2020). Moreover, fishers nowadays need to pay for some fuel, and a FCA staff [102501] explained, “FCA used to cover the price of cruise ship fuel, but after the increase in Fuel prices, cruise ship activities were left to the fishermen themselves, so they had to bear part of the fuel price themselves.”

3.3.2 FCAs

There are FCAs in each JSSF community to support fishers’ activities. According to Lou and Yu (2022), FCAs are currently the backbone of Shizuoka's fishing community's business organizations. Their role as self-help social enterprises is significant in alleviating social conflicts, enhancing market functions, and providing administrative benefits. FCAs are also vital for their ability to facilitate connections with other regional organizations and officials, ensuring strong succession and risk management and building a spirit of mutual support for resource reintegration. Delaney (2015) also says the beginning of FCA consolidation was in the 1970s. Although fishers are facing a fallen condition of the traditional SSF, Umigyo tourism can help them maintain their image and existence to the public. According to Li and Lou (2018), the Umigyo activities give fishermen a positive reputation for becoming a key body of coastal governance in Japan.

Regarding the FCAs’ efforts and missions in Umigyo Tourism, they play a major role in the management of fishers for their benefit. Logistical support through the necessary supplies for fishers is a basic membership benefit after fishers pay the money to be members (Li & Namikawa, 2020). A common example is its offered ice with containers that preserve freshness [102103 & 120805], which is also used in tourism activities when tourists are allowed to watch fishers catching fish [121801]. Similarly to indoor education, a fisher interviewee as a class instructor [120602] ensured that the FCA also brings opportunities for classroom teaching and learning. Consequently, fishers are more likely to participate in Umigyo Tourism when they see the material support. Meanwhile, FCAs also have a heavy-duty of marketing the Umigyo Tourism activities, but some fishers feel insufficient publicity due to their weak promotional skills [120101 & 120601]. At the same time, the activities are only decided by FCAs instead of the government [121801]. FCAs also protect their members' rights, especially in conflicts. FCAs in the co-management system, with frequent contact with the government, assist in communications and conflicts for the pursuit of equity and fairness (Delaney, 2015). In particular, a fisher [120804] said that FCAs have fought for SSF's rights for years when LSF's overfishing harmed the overall fish catch of the SSFs.

3.3.3 Tourism Agencies (With A Weaker Empowerment)

Tourism agencies are not a common stakeholder group in Umigyo Tourism anymore. The tourism associations used to emphasize marketing and the improvement of marine projects and activities (Lou, 2013/2022), but their sense of presence and power has dissipated a lot recently as FCAs have taken responsibility for tourism marketing with strategies of plans [112801 & 120601]. At the same time, the tourism agencies’ financial orientation and unfair profit allocation to fishers, rather than the original purpose of nature tourism, cannot match fishers’ desire, so some tourism agencies quit the coastal tourism business in some JSSF communities, such as most of those in Miyagi [FG 20231130]. However, there are still some tourism agencies left. According to an official in Shizuoka [121801], “Although Umigyo relies much less on tourism agencies, tourism agencies still remain and play an important role in some areas to cooperate with SSF communities for promotion.” As a consequence, the presence and significance of tourism associations vary across different regions in the JSSF communities in their efforts to develop Umigyo Tourism, with a noticeable declining trend.

3.3.4 Government

There are some new innovations after the implementation of Japan's Sixth Industrialization Policy made by Japan's government. The adapted version of Sixth Industrialization activities forms a food system with businesses combining the agriculture, forestry, and fisheries industries, such as direct sales, direct delivery from the SSF households, and a fisher's restaurant (Nakano, 2014). Prefecture governments are the key stakeholders that are deeply involved in the Umigyo Tourism execution for funding support, fisher training, and destination design to respond to the Sixth Industrialization Policy. Some of their political support is through subsidies, such as the post-disaster reconstruction [121801] and the operation of educational and tourism activities in JSSF communities [102501]. For example, the government offered funding for Nori fishers to let them work together for 3 years to recover their aquaculture after the 3.11 Earthquake in Higashi Matsushima [120201], while the payment for fishers' guide of community visits in Tagonoura is through governmental funding [102501]. At the same time, the government provided training for fishers during the previous Nagisahaku Tourism and Hamakatsu Tourism, which were elements of Umigyo Tourism [120101], and the MAFF departments continue to give training to fishermen in fishing and tourism [FG 20231130].

Moreover, the government's Destination Management Organization (DMO) department also works on tourism attraction planning to attract tourists from other countries, including the Umigyo destination design [FG 20231130]. According to Chang and Katrichis (2016), destination management organizations, which include missions of promotion of destination image, marketing, infrastructure, and transport facilities supply chain management, aim to decrease social, cultural and environmental harm by making the gap between visitors and locals closer. Research has shown that the high focus on DMOs at local, state, regional, and national levels can be reflected by the Japanese government's new DMO program called 'Registered DMO Candidate Program in Japan,' and the Japanese government, which expects to build an image of a 'tourism-oriented developed nation' set an aim to attract 40 million international tourists by 2020 and 60 million international tourists by 2030 (Nagai et al., 2018). Thus, the government cares about both the beauty and the service staff to enhance the destination image.

3.3.5 Power Dynamics among Main Stakeholders

There is smooth communication during Japan's major coastal stakeholder groups' power dynamics (shown in Figure 4). In terms of the issuance of new policies and regulations, a Shizuoka official [121801] explained, "The Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries (MAFF) in the national government sets and administers the policies for the Prefectures, while the prefectures adapt the policies and deliver them to the FCAs so that FCAs can follow the Umigyo policies." According to Li and Namikawa (2020), JSSF's top-down hierarchy is the authority from the national government to the prefecture government to the FCAs. In order to ensure the central government and prefecture government are on the same page, the official [121801] also points out that some officials at the national level are assigned to the grassroots level for a period of time at the prefectural level to better contact and understand the nearby JSSF communities. FCAs are in the middle between the prefecture-level government, as research explains that it assigns FCAs the right to the resource, and the local fishers, who are entitled as members by the local FCA to use their rights to resources in the area of the local FCA (Delaney, 2015). A majority of economic earnings for FCAs still rely on the handling fee to help fishers sell fish [121501].

In contrast to the top-down direction, the fishers with membership can give opinions to their corresponding FCA. According to a fisherman [120804], although the FCAs in some other countries are money-making bureaucracies without concerns or even interactions with SSF fishers, this kind of complaint never happens in Japan. For example, according to a fisher in Mochimune [120702], pleasure boats are also under the governance of FCA; after fishers reported a pleasure boat accidentally cut an SSF boat's net in the Shirasu-catching zone, SSF soon made a rule: when SSF is doing its catch of Shirasu, pleasure boats cannot enter

the Shirasu-fishing zone until SSF boats fish their catch. FCA staff often host some guides to university professors and students, prefectural and local government officials, and other relevant specialists, and sometimes display Projects they are proud of, such as the canteen in Tagonoura and the marine cruise and cooking classes in Yui [011601]. The official [121801] said the official staff in the grassroots projects would record the cases he visited at the prefectural level, such as Yui, and report how the Umigyo policies match the specific cases to the central government.

Figure 4

Hierarchical Style of Management among Common Stakeholder Groups

Source: Based on data from semi-structured interviews with prefectural officials, FCA staff, fishers, and marine academic specialists.

3.3.6 Community-Specific Stakeholders

There are some community-specific stakeholder groups that are present in only a few communities. In particular, there is a Marine Leisure League for danger alleviation, the Intermediate Support Organization for incubator, support, and infrastructure management, the women's groups for food preparation, and diving-related business operators for equipment rental (Lou, 2013/2022). Noticeably, the voluntary shore rescue group is able to sustain itself due to the strong spontaneity of these community members and small grants in the form of gifts from the local FCA [011601]. Meanwhile, the women's groups are playing a more significant role because their waste reduction, workshop operation creation of women's working opportunities, and traditional food inheritance match Umigyo Tourism's value of culture and business protection and nature education outreach [120401].

3.4 First Order

The first order of justice represents the interactions between stakeholder groups, which includes both problems and opportunities (Nayak, 2022). There is a high level of justice due to the harmony of the collaboration among stakeholder groups. Delaney (2015) confirms the successful co-management in Japan with governmental and political support to enhance the capabilities of local fishers and communities. There are different kinds of interactions among the government (national and prefectural level), FCA in each community, and fishers, and other local stakeholders.

There is more collaboration of stakeholders for students as the targets of marine education in Japan. Compared with Pescatourism's emphasis on the physical experiential to achieve its educational aim, which regards fishing on board as a main experiential activity to arouse fishers' interest in local cultural and natural resources (Muñoz, 2018; Saba, 2013), Umigyo Tourism combines it with indoor education in their communities, especially when students are a considerable target market. Meanwhile, Japan's education system cared about contact with nature [FG 20240116]. Thus, Japanese Umigyo Tourism has built tight cooperation with accessible underage students from one class to another instead of relying on the adults' consumption from other prefectures.

3.4.1 Conflicts

Nayak (2022) explains the first order as interactions among stakeholder groups based on the current power structure, including negotiation for problem-solving and collaborations for viability. Regarding the external conflicts, Li and Lou (2018) explained that as fishery entirely relies on fishery resources, there are conflicts over space for pleasure boats and sailing, conflicts on resources for recreational fishing, and conflicts on both space and resources for scuba diving and renewable energy development. An outstanding long-lasting example of the resources is that LSFs' overfishing leaves a lower volume of fish in the coastal regions for SSF communities, so the SSF fishers complain about LSFs' unsustainable fishing catching that harms the biodiversity [120804]. Another conflict about SSF space is that recreational tourists' behaviours that overlap with fishers' activity areas continue, which leads to subsequent environmental problems like the plastic garbage left (Lou & Yu, 2022; Li & Lou, 2018). These conflicts between stakeholder groups need to be mitigated through continuous interactions.

3.4.2 Collaborations

There are some active collaborations among the local stakeholder groups, shown in Figure 5.

The cooperation between fishers and primary/middle schools was implemented in 2006 (Li & Namikawa, 2020). Some governmental actions promoting ecotourism in Japan match Umigyo projects for marine education, which requires collaboration between different stakeholder groups. There is popular maritime education for young children. For example, Hinase Junior High School (HJHS) in Bizen City has a formal marine education program (Sakurai et al., 2019), and the coastal area of Otsuchi located in the Sanriku region has an environmental education program for not only elementary and high school students but also for residents (Sakurai et al., 2016). Umigyo has allowed more innovation in its teaching style, such as the Fish Cooking Class in Yui about teaching students how to deal with fish meat [120602]. Similarly, the ecotourism curriculum is encouraged to be included in Japan's adult education to match the UN's sustainable development (Uzama & Walter, 2018). As a result, the motivation for marine education leads more people to experience Umigyo.

Figure 5

JSSFs' Cooperation with Stakeholder Groups.

Source: Based on data are from observation, literature, semi-structured interviews answered by FCAs, JSSF fishers, marine academic specialists, restaurant and seafood manufacturing staff, and prefectural marine officials, and focus groups answered by marine officials, and tourists who experienced Umigyo Tourism.

The JSSF's cooperation with higher education institutions brings students with knowledge to the JSSF communities to facilitate their revitalization. In terms of the universities' efforts for fishers, a marine-related professor [011601] said, "Some of the students from the marine-related departments will bring these communities the Umigyo knowledge of business and marketing to help them." The previous alumni, who have already worked in the JSSF-related institutions, sometimes return to the universities to share their experiences with the current students. For example, a staff member in the Shizuoka Prefecture Fisheries Federation [112801] realized the current university courses are too broad and talk about the wide Japanese scale rather than Shizuoka's fisheries, so he joined the lectures to let students understand the fisheries in Shizuoka Prefecture. There is also a Fisheries Higher School, like a college with a one-year course to cultivate fishing techniques, in Shizuoka, which contributes around 20 students to their careers in different ports in Shizuoka every year; as the Shizuoka government offers the academic aid of the Fisheries Higher School, the working range for these students is also Shizuoka [121801].

Among fishers, they normally get along with each other for space and knowledge sharing in the study sites. When fishing, both officials [FG 20231130] agreed that there are almost no conflicts for the overlapping regions of trap, fixed nets, aquaculture, and gillnet within a JSSF community in Higashi Matsushima. Likewise, a Mochimune fisher [102103] was proud that fishermen have good relationships and are willing to share and help each other by telling other local fishermen when they find fish. In addition, young fishers can learn techniques from the elderly for faster growth of skills [120101]. Thus, there is frequent communication and contact among fishers in the same community to support each other. There are several cases in which different ports are willing to make the collaboration led to information and resource exchange. In particular, Shin-Monato and Yui are two close SSF ports that catch shrimps. Shin-Monato can catch white shrimps in its zone, while Yui only catches red shrimps. The frequent collaboration between Yui and Shin-Monato to catch Sakura shrimps builds a tight relationship among fishers, even though they are under different FCAs [120601 & 011601]. In addition to the exchange of resources, the current governance arrangements allow different scales of interaction for the exchange of insights and innovation

among fishers. There are meetings among local young fishers twice per year to exchange their information and ideas, as well as yearly national-scale meetings in Tokyo to let fishers share their feelings and challenges [120804]. Thus, JSSF fishers have the motivation and chances to build networks with other fishers through fishing collaboration and meetings, which is helpful for young successors' growth and enthusiasm.

Fishers' relationship with hotels is cooperation rather than competition. There are hotels close to some JSSF communities that do not have fisher-operated accommodations. According to a prefectural official [121801], these hotels solve tourists' concerns about overnight trips and give female SSF community members the chance to work to gain money. Thus, fishers and hotels have mutual benefits during both on and off seasons.

The seafood processing factories have a tight and vital relationship with fishers, and the one in Mochimune is an outstanding example. The global trend, the idea to differentiate the product from other products, and the desire to make customers taste the clean food and feel the duty of a high hygiene level inspired the business of processing Shirasu in Mochimune [120701]. The machine operators in the factory are external employees, not fishermen. Therefore, the effort required by fishermen during the processing step will be greatly reduced. When fishermen realize this win-win approach, they express their gratitude to these partners and hope to continue this relationship [102103]. The existence of the processing factory brings Mochimune's Shirasu brand to some big cities, such as Tokyo and Hokkaido, and the raw material management on paper for traceability, which is detailed enough for food safety to trace which boat, which day, and which zone of the Ocean did the fish come from and can also bring a sense of security for the customers [120701]. Nowadays, the most used sales channel for the products is 7.11 because the certified products are in a well-known chain store [120701]. As a result, the fast growth of the processing factory and the community's positive attitude have raised the whole community's reputation through high-quality seafood.

The former supply relationship between fishermen and restaurants can be maintained and made closer through Umigyo's innovation. The local restaurants which purchase the caught fish can be categorized as the stakeholder groups due to their mutual benefits from the growing number of tourists attracted by Umigyo Tourism. Admittedly, the fishers are the operators of Umigyo Tourism which is an element of Umigyo. However, some restaurants are owned by local residents, so they are the common stakeholders for Umigyo. For example, some FCAs hold their seafood restaurant and direct sale stores as another income channel, so they also play the role of fish buyers for local fishers [102104]. As fish buyers, they buy the fish in the morning for freshness, right after fishers finish catching fish and return to the port [120802]. Since Umigyo Tourism is expected to maintain the fishing industry in each JSSF community, it will lead to the maintenance of nearby restaurants and massive jobs for local people.

3.4.3 Spontaneity and Mission

Umigyo represents justice for every JSSF fisher, as the utilization of both fishery resources and every kind of regional marine-related resources is probably the most possible method for the SSF viability for Japan, which also matches the global trend of Blue Justice well. At the same time, some JSSF communities face urgent challenges. For example, an experienced fisher [102103] sighed that Mochimune may disband in two years if there is no successor, expressing eagerly, "Different types of development plans must have alternative opportunities, and we cannot just talk about it on paper; we must not only think about it but also take practical actions to implement it." Likely wise, community members [120804 & 120101 & 120601 & 102501] in all other study sites have a strong awareness of the revitalization as a prior mission. Due to the worse condition of the fishing industry, fishers have to try different possible industries and activities in JSSF communities for the mission of revitalization, and Umigyo is the most realistic option.

There are several JSSF communities with several fishers who have a high spontaneity for Umigyo. In Higashi Matsushima, Umigyo Tourism is the top-tier passion as more fishermen are willing to join the fishing tourism industry, and their unity helped them successfully resist the unfair distribution of benefits from outsiders [FG 20231130]. Fishers set a uniform price for guesthouses, which was lower than the outsiders, to fight against commercial tourism and force the outsider tourism agencies to leave. In other communities, Tagonoura witnesses high participation of SSF families [102501], and the Umigyo Tourism activities in Higashiizu have become the major motivator of young successors. Regarding Yui as a community in the rehabilitation stage of Umigyo Tourism after disasters, there is an increasing desire to try to restart their previous Umigyo activities with up-to-date strategies, and FCA can hear the voices of their inspirations [120601 & 120603]. Thus, fishers in many communities express their enthusiasm for expanding the Umigyo market's size.

On the contrary, there is no unity of fishers' opinion toward the Umigyo Business in some communities, especially Mochimune. A seafood processor [120701] witnessed that some people here are not interested in joining Umigyo, so its development will happen slowly until more fishers accept it. Similarly, there is a lack of consensus on FCA's efforts. According to a fisher [102103], some fishermen have solidified their minds and believe that the Fisheries Association is unnecessary, but they are not aware that they would not even be able to make ice to preserve the fishers without the local FCA. In a fisher's [102103] and a processor's [120701] opinions, it may be promoted as time passes because although older fishers prefer competition, younger fishers prefer harmony, justice, and fairness without a strong sense of territoriality.

4. Conclusions

Umigyo Tourism in Japan is similar to Pescaturism, which is accepted by many JSSF fishers to some degree and has become a political act. The collaboration with schools for a high focus on marine education through Umigyo Tourism deserves Pescaturism to learn to enhance justice in Italy. It is both a motivator and a goal of the Umigyo Tourism governance. With the government's support and FCAs' efforts, Japan prescribes the right medicine through its meta order, which is to alleviate its most urgent successor problem by education to spread JSSF's social contributions and value to the youth as well as boosting the activity diversity to decrease the stigma of fishers' harsh working environment. As the co-management brings an active information exchange in power dynamics among main stakeholder groups, the positive performance of the second order can lead to more practical institutional policies and actions. Finally, the positive environment of coastal institutions, which supports fishers' value promotion, results in sufficient interactions among local stakeholder groups and active negotiation for conflict-solving.

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Vulnerability to Viability (V2V) Global Partnership

The Vulnerability to Viability (V2V) project is a transdisciplinary global partnership and knowledge network. Our aim is to support the transition of small-scale fisheries (SSF) from vulnerability to viability in Africa and Asia. Vulnerability is understood as a function of exposure, sensitivity and the capacity to respond to diverse drivers of change. We use the term viability not just in an its economic sense but also to include its social, political, and ecological dimensions.

The V2V partnership brings together approximately 150 people and 70 organizations across six countries in Asia (Bangladesh, India, Indonesia, Japan, Malaysia, Thailand), six countries in Africa (Ghana, Malawi, Nigeria, Senegal, South Africa, Tanzania), Canada and globally. This unique initiative is characterized by diverse cultural and disciplinary perspectives, extensive capacity building and graduate student training activities, and grounded case studies from two regions of the world to show how and when SSF communities can proactively respond to challenges and creatively engage in solutions that build their viability. Further information on the V2V Partnership is available here: www.v2vglobalpartnership.org.

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